

MODELLING THE BEHAVIOUR OF GAS BUBBLES IN EPOXY RESIN

Jonathan R. Wood

Michael G. Bader

Composite Materials Research Group

Department of Materials Science and Engineering

University of Surrey

Guildford, Surrey, Great Britain.

ABSTRACT

The behaviour of bubbles containing a non-condensable gas in an uncured unmodified bisphenol-A resin has been studied. The investigation involved the monitoring of bubbles and the subsequent modelling of their behaviour utilising mass diffusion equations. A novel method of measuring the diffusion coefficient of gases in epoxy resin has been employed based on the observation of bubble dissolution rates. The effect of temperature, concentration of gas in solution and initial bubble size have been shown to affect the time to complete solution of gas bubbles.

KEY WORDS : Bubbles; Epoxy Resin; Modelling; Diffusion; Porosity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Porosity in composite materials is a direct result of the fabrication process and can have a profound effect on the mechanical properties of the final composite part. Porosity is the consequence of entrapped air from the resin mixing operation and lay-up procedures, water within the resin and organic volatiles emanating from the chemical components that make up the thermosetting matrix. Air bubbles present in the uncured composite can act as sites for the diffusion of these volatile species causing the bubbles to grow. The curing of epoxy resin based composites involves changes in pressure (and vacuum) and temperature. An increase in temperature and the application of a vacuum bag, as used in the prepreg autoclave processing route, can cause the gas within the bubble to expand in accordance with the Gas Laws. Applying a vacuum also decreases the saturated gas concentration, with respect to the concentration under ambient conditions, which is governed by Henry's law. This increases the driving force for diffusion of gas from solution into an existing bubble.

There are two fundamental steps involved in the formation of a bubble of visible size. They are nucleation and growth. Bubbles nucleate from small cavities (nuclei) and grow as a consequence of diffusion. The degree of supersaturation and the nature of the substrate both affect the rate of nucleation and the radius of the critical nuclei. After bubbles have formed

the next stage is the growth of these bubbles. When a nucleated bubble attains a certain minimum size it will grow until the pressure inside is in equilibrium with the external pressure of the liquid. The equilibrium force balance is:

$$\Delta P = \frac{2\gamma}{R} \quad (1)$$

where

ΔP is the difference in pressure

γ is the surface tension

R is the radius of the bubble

It is reasonable to assume that in a composite system heterogeneous nuclei will always exist and that if the resin is supersaturated with gas, nucleation and growth of bubbles will occur. Mechanically entrapped bubbles also act as sites for the diffusion of gas molecules and volatile species present in the resin. Both these processes will encourage bubble growth. Once the resin has reached the gel point bubbles in the composite are effectively "frozen" and will remain in the final composite laminate. Bubbles in a composite system do not have the option of escaping to the high points in the system due to the network of fibres that present a virtually impregnable barrier to an otherwise buoyant bubble. Elimination of bubbles in the composite has subsequently to occur in situ thus requiring a thorough appreciation of the collapse kinetics and the parameters that affect the dissolution of gas bubbles in epoxy resins. The ultimate aim of this investigation is to develop a model that can be used as 'shop floor' tool that can determine the process parameters in the cure cycle which will ensure a pore-free laminate. The modelling and the input variables must therefore be based on fundamental scientific principles and easily measured materials data.

2. DIFFUSION CONTROLLED BUBBLE COLLAPSE

A gas bubble in a liquid-gas solution will grow or shrink according to whether the solution is oversaturated or undersaturated. The mathematical formulation for this process clearly consists of the diffusion equation in the liquid

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} + \frac{R^2}{r^2} R \cdot \frac{\partial C}{\partial r} = \frac{D}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial C}{\partial r} \right) \quad (2)$$

where

D is the diffusion coefficient of the gas in the liquid

C is the concentration of gas in the liquid at a point r

r is a spherical co-ordinate from the centre of the bubble

R is the radius of the bubble at any time t .

and $R \cdot$ is the change of bubble radius with time.

The transport term on the left hand side of equation 2 has been omitted in the following analysis since the bubble wall velocities are low in a resin system. This is primarily a consequence of the low value of D within the temperature range under consideration.

An approximate solution based on this simplification was obtained by Epstein & Plesset [1] who considered a spherical bubble in an infinite isotropic medium. Their result takes the form

$$RR' = D \left(\frac{C_{\infty} - C_s}{\rho_g} \right) [1 + R(\pi Dt)^{-1/2}] \quad (3)$$

where

C_{∞} is the dissolved gas concentration,

C_s is the gas concentration at saturation

and ρ_g is the density of gas within the bubble.

The second term in the equation reflects the transient effect of the build-up of a diffusion boundary layer that quickly becomes large compared to the bubble itself. Under these circumstances the size of the bubble is of little consequence as far as the configuration of the surrounding concentration is concerned. The bubble size is important insofar as it determines the interfacial area across which mass transfer between phases takes place. Equation 3 implies that the time for complete solution of a gas bubble is proportional to R_0^2 , where R_0 is the initial radius of the bubble at $t=0$. It also implies that in a saturated solution i.e. $C_{\infty}/C_s=1$, the time for a bubble to dissolve completely is infinite. In the system investigated neither of these factors were found to be the case. In the absence of surface tension a bubble would be stable against the transport of gas in a saturated solution, however, because of surface tension the bubble actually dissolves. An extended model was therefore used in which surface tension forces were taken into account.

An approximate solution of the diffusion equation for this case is given by:

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = -Dd \frac{1-f+\tau/(R\rho(\infty))}{1+2\tau/(3R\rho(\infty))} \left[\frac{1}{R} + \frac{1}{(\pi Dt)^{1/2}} \right] \quad (4)$$

$$d = C_s / [\rho(\infty) + \tau/R] \quad (5)$$

where

$\rho(\infty)$ is density of the gas with a gas-liquid interface of zero curvature.

τ $2M\gamma/R_gT$

M is the molecular mass of the gas

γ is the surface tension

R_g is the universal gas constant
 T is the temperature,

$$f = \frac{C_m}{C_s} \quad (6)$$

In a saturated solution $f=1$ and equation 3 reduces to:

$$1 - \left(\frac{R}{R_o}\right)^3 + \delta \left(1 - \left(\frac{R}{R_o}\right)^2\right) = \left(\frac{3\delta}{2}\right) x^2 \quad (7)$$

where

$$x^2 = (2Dd/R_o^2)t$$

and $\delta = \tau/R_o\rho_{(w)}$

and the time for complete solution is given by

$$t = \frac{R_o^2 P_L M}{3DR_g T C_s} \left(\frac{R_o P_L}{2\gamma} + 1 \right) \quad (8)$$

where P_L is the pressure acting on the liquid.

It becomes apparent that in order to model the behaviour of gas bubbles in a resin system a number of input parameters are required, namely the diffusion coefficient D , the saturation concentration of the gas C_s and the concentration of the gas dissolved in the resin C_d , the surface tension for the resin-gas combination, and the initial size of the bubble. Some of these parameters are affected by the temperatures and pressures experienced in the composite processing route.

3. EVALUATION OF THE INPUT VARIABLES

3.1 Saturation concentration C_s The solubility of gases in polymers only increases slightly with temperature due to the low heat of solution. It has been assumed that the saturation concentration is constant over the temperature range under consideration. The value of C_s is given by Henry's law which establishes the connection between the partial pressure P_g of a gas acting on a liquid surface and the equilibrium concentration

$$C_s = P_g/k \quad (9)$$

where

k is Henry's law constant for the particular system

3.1.1 Measurement of C_s Values for Henry's law constant were not in the literature for the gas/resin system in question. The saturation concentration was measured using an instantaneous vacuum technique. A quantity of resin containing the dissolved gas was placed in a graduated container and heated to reduce its viscosity. The initial volume of resin was measured. The resin was then placed under a virtually instantaneous vacuum.

The resin foams under this vacuum as the gas is precipitated from solution. The immediate change in volume is effectively a result of gas expansion and application of the ideal gas law yields the concentration of gas present in the resin under ambient conditions. For the system under investigation the saturation concentration at atmospheric pressure was 0.0207 kg/m^3 . If Henry's law is obeyed, which is probable when dealing with such low concentrations, k for nitrogen in resin is similar to that of nitrogen in aromatic liquids [2].

3.2 Diffusion coefficient D The diffusion coefficient is a function of temperature and viscosity. The composite processing route involves heating which reduces the resin viscosity and ultimately leads to the curing reaction which will have the reverse effect. It was necessary not only to determine the diffusion coefficient for gas molecules in resin but also its temperature dependence. It was assumed that the diffusion coefficient was independent of concentration which is reasonable for most small molecule diffusion systems [3].

3.2.1 Measurement of the Diffusion Coefficient D The diffusion coefficient was measured by observing bubble dissolution rates in a saturated epoxy resin. Saturating the epoxy with nitrogen at atmospheric pressure and 313K eliminated the variable C_{∞} in equation 4 and subsequently the driving force for diffusion were the surface tension forces.

Using equation 5 it was possible to model the shrinkage of the bubbles and determine the diffusion coefficient at the experimental temperature. This was repeated for a number of temperatures (figure 1). It was found that the activation energy for diffusion of nitrogen in the resin was higher than expected (77 kJ/mole) although it is believed that this is purely a consequence of the changing viscosity. This is in agreement with molecular friction theory [4]. At higher temperatures the change in viscosity with temperature is less dramatic and the diffusion coefficient was found to increase at a slower rate.

As both viscous flow and diffusion are controlled by the same friction constant, factors which change D will change the viscosity η in a similar manner. Figure 1 implies that the true activation energy for diffusion may be obtained from the slope at higher temperatures i.e. when the viscosity change with temperature is lower. The value of activation energy E_a in this region (37.5 kJ/mole) is in agreement with typical values of E_a in polymer melts [5]. In the lower temperature range the activation energy although equally valid in determining the diffusion coefficient of the gas in the resin is primarily a consequence of the changing viscosity.

3.3 Surface tension γ This was measured using a capillary rise method and was found to decrease slightly over temperature range of the experiments. A value of 0.035 N/m was found to be in agreement with most gas/polymer systems [6].

3.4 Dissolved gas concentration C_{∞} This was measured using the same method as determining the saturation gas concentration. This parameter is the

dissolved gas concentration prior to the processing and will remain relatively constant throughout the cure cycle.

4. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

All experiments were performed on an unmodified bisphenol-A resin (Shell 828) and the gas injected was pure dry nitrogen. The resin had initially been placed under vacuum at an elevated temperature to remove any water that

might have entered the system. The resin was subsequently stored in a desiccator containing silica gel to prevent moisture absorption from humid air. This ensured that the bubbles monitored in the experiments contained pure dry gas with a negligible moisture component.

4.1 Dissolving Gas In order to determine the saturation concentration of nitrogen in the resin and perform the saturated resin experiments it was necessary to thoroughly saturate the resin with the gas. This was carried out at atmospheric pressure and at 313K. Dry nitrogen gas was bubbled through the resin for 48 hours and then any bubbles were allowed to separate out before the concentration was measured. It was imperative that only the dissolved gas content of the resin was measured and not any suspended gas in the form of microscopic bubbles.

4.2 Gas injection Gas was introduced into the resin by injecting a small amount from a gas bottle. Bubbling was done at a pressure sufficient to introduce small gas bubbles into the resin.

4.3 Monitoring Bubble Collapse The resin containing suspended bubbles in a glass cuvette with transparent flat sides was placed on a heating stage of an optical microscope. The heat source was a halogen lamp which also acted as a back light. The temperature was measured using a thermocouple and photographs were taken at regular intervals to monitor changes in bubble size.

4.4 Analysis of Data For monitoring numerous bubbles an image analysis technique has proved successful. The contrast between the bubbles and the resin enables each photograph to be analysed showing the distribution of bubble sizes in the sample.

Figure 1 Determining the diffusion coefficient at various temperatures

5. DISCUSSION

Bubbles containing a non condensable gas such as nitrogen in resin decrease in size with time if the diffusion kinetics are favourable (figure 2). The rate of dissolution is increased at higher temperatures (figure 3) and when the dissolved gas concentration is lower. Bubbles may collapse even in saturated solutions due to the effects of surface tension forces.

In undersaturated solutions there is an initial deviation from the model due to the build-up of a diffusion boundary layer adjacent to the bubble (figure 4).

As a consequence the rate of dissolution initially decreases with time but then it increases with time which has been attributed to two competing effects. In the first place the concentration gradient at the interface decreases with time due to increased gas concentration in the solution near the interface. This influence is most important at short times when the gradient is decreasing sharply from its original infinite value. At this time the rate of dissolution is theoretically approximately proportional to $t^{-1/2}$ from equation 3.

As the bubble becomes small the dissolution rate again increases as now the interfacial area of the bubble becomes markedly less than the diffusion boundary layer. Since the total flux at the bubble surface is affected by the area available for diffusion throughout the diffusion zone, when the bubble radius is small, in comparison to the radius of the diffusion zone, this effect will dominate over the influence of increased gas concentration and the rate of bubble shrinkage will tend to increase. The cumulative effect of the transient is that the

Figure 2 Gas bubbles decrease in size with time

Figure 3 The rate of gas bubble dissolution increases with temperature

times for complete solution will be overestimated by the model. This deviation from the steady state solution was not observed with the bubbles in a saturated solution which was a good indication that saturation had been attained. This was also the reason for measuring the diffusion coefficient in a saturated solution.

Figure 4 The build up of a diffusion boundary layer affects the rate of bubble collapse

The model appears to fit the data. The diffusion coefficients were calculated from the times for complete solution in equation 7 so although it was inevitable that these points would fit the model it is relatively apparent from figures 2 and 3 that the model is in good agreement with the rest of the curve. Figure 4 shows the behaviour of a gas bubble in an undersaturated solution. In this case the parameters entered into the model were purely the material parameters of the system; the surface tension, the dissolved and saturated concentration, the temperature and pressure and the diffusion coefficient taken from figure 1.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Simple bubble experiments of this type yield a great deal of information about the behaviour of gas bubbles in resin. With a knowledge of the diffusion coefficient, surface tension force and gas concentrations it is possible to determine whether a gas bubble will grow or dissolve as well as predicting the time for complete solution. Empiricism is minimal in the model and although the values of the input parameters will vary between resin systems the theory should apply equally to other similar systems. Measurement of these input parameters is also a simple characterisation process and the methods outlined for determining the diffusion coefficient and the gas concentrations are time and cost efficient.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS :

The work was supported by Rolls Royce plc and we gratefully acknowledge the useful discussions with Dr J Johnson and Dr W R Jones.

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